

Study of Solid State Reaction Between Mercuric Chloride and Sodium Tungstate

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IN the reactivity of solids, exchange reactions are of immense interest. However, because of their complicated nature limited number of such reactions have been studied and their mechanism is also not well understood. In the reaction between MgO and $ZnWO_4$, Jander¹ interpreted the reaction as due to solid state diffusion while Rastogi and Dubey² suggested the possibility of vapour phase diffusion in the reaction between mercuric chloride and iodine. The kinetics of such reactions are governed by different mechanisms, depending upon whether the rate determining step is the phase boundary reaction, diffusion process or nucleation³⁻⁵. In order to examine kinetics and elucidate the mechanism of such reactions, the solid state reaction between $HgCl_2$ and $Na_2WO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$ has been studied.

Experimental

AnalaR $HgCl_2$ and $Na_2WO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$ were separately powdered and sieved through mesh.

Fig. 1. Plots of ξ versus t in reaction between $HgCl_2$ and $Na_2WO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$ for reactant particles of size below 74 microns at different temperatures.

Reaction between $HgCl_2$ and $Na_2WO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$: Mercuric chloride and sodium tungstate particles of known size were filled in glass tubes (0.8 dia. x 10 cm), the former from one end and the latter from the other end, so that the reactants have sharp contact at the centre of the tube. The tubes were sealed at one end and were subjected to a constant pressure (4 kg cm^{-2}) at the other end. The tubes were then placed in a thermostat ($\pm 0.1^\circ$). A yellow coloured product layer appeared at the point of contact and was marked to ascertain the direction of diffusion. It was observed that only mercuric chloride diffused through the product layer to react with the other reactant at the product/sodium tungstate interface. The length of the product layer was measured with a travelling microscope (least count $\pm 0.002 \text{ cm}$) after certain intervals of time. The experiment was repeated for different temperatures. The data are plotted in Fig. 1.

Role of vapour phase diffusion: The reactants were filled in a glass tube to leave some air gap between the two reactants. The tube was kept in a thermostat (100°) and after 3 h it was observed that the reaction occurred on the side of sodium tungstate only. This suggested the occurrence of vapour phase diffusion of mercuric chloride which caused the reaction on the side of sodium tungstate. However, the contribution of the vapour phase diffusion is not substantial.

X-Ray diffraction: Mercuric chloride and sodium tungstate were mixed in equimolar ratio by grinding in cyclohexane and heated for 12 h at 100° with intermediate grindings. The X-ray diffractogram of the sample gives the following d values (\AA) with the relative intensities given in parenthesis. 8.34 (14), 6.66 (5), 5.27 (75), 4.69 (8), 4.55 (4), 4.48 (5), 4.35 (51), 4.09 (16), 3.75 (7), 3.58 (5), 3.44 (7), 3.38 (17), 3.22 (96), 3.07 (4), 3.03 (5), 2.99 (20), 2.90 (5), 2.75 (100), 2.71 (13), 2.41 (11), 2.13 (7), 2.09 (13), 2.06 (9), 1.99 (8), 1.94 (7), 1.90 (5), 1.86 (35), 1.75 (27), 1.62 (23), 1.54 (13), 1.44 (13), 1.40 (7), 1.28 (6), 1.22 (10) and 1.18 (12).

The sample prepared for X-ray diffraction studies, was washed with distilled water and then dried under vacuum and analysed for Hg by the usual method. The results suggest the formula of the product as $HgWO_4$.

Results and Discussion

The kinetic data of the reaction, as evident from the Fig. 1, follows the linear equation

$$\xi = kt + C,$$

where ξ is the thickness of the product column at any time t , k is the specific reaction rate constant and C is another constant. The k values, calculated from the Fig. 1, are 18.70×10^{-3} , 21.43×10^{-3} and $27.28 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm h}^{-1}$ at 90, 100 and 110° , respectively and the corresponding C values are 8.50×10^{-3} , 20.00×10^{-3} and $25.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}$. The energy

of activation as calculated from the Arrhenius plot, is $6.5 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$.

The X-ray diffraction data of the product when compared with the known data for NaCl, suggest the presence of NaCl in addition to some other compounds. The experimental d values 3.22 (95), 2.75 (100), 1.99 (10), 1.75 (27), 1.62 (23), 1.40 (7), 1.28 (6), 1.22 (10) and 1.18 \AA (12) correspond to the NaCl structure. Formation of NaCl suggests the stoichiometry of the reaction to be

However, the X-ray diffraction data for HgWO_4 could not be traced either from the powder diffraction file or from the literature.

The applicability of the linear equation shows that the reaction kinetics are controlled by the phase boundary reaction and the diffusion occurs unhindered⁴⁻⁶. The product layer is porous and does not offer any resistance to the diffusion. The low value of the energy of activation $6.5 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ substantiates it to be a phase boundary controlled reaction. Substantial increase in C values with rise in temperature suggests vigorous initial reaction at the interface.

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Effect of Particle Size on the Kinetics of Thermal Dehydration of Silicic Acid Hydrogel

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It is generally agreed¹ that the gelation of silica hydrogel is a function of the silica units. Silicic acid hydrogel, normally prepared by destabilisation of an aqueous solution of sodium silicate, has been used as a dehydrating agent in various processes.

The phenomena of crystallisation of silicic acid hydrogel which is analogous to the natural ageing of gels to hyalite, opal, chert, chalcedony, etc., has been studied² extensively by X-ray diffraction with refined DTA and dilatometric method. The surface properties of the silicic acid hydrogel are independent of the state of crystallinity³. It was observed⁴ that the first small losses of bound water occur at 150° followed by a continuous dehydroxylation above 380° .

The kinetic approach to the study of thermal decomposition of many hydrated materials depends on the rates of reaction and in addition gives basic information about the materials, their structure, surfaces and so forth. It was found⁵ that the rate constant during zeolitic dehydration followed an inverse relationship with the total water content of the samples and was explained in terms of position of water molecules in the lattice. It was also shown that the loosely bound channel water also influences strongly but is much less than that of coordinated water. The dehydration kinetics study on alumino-silicate hydrogel⁶, taking four different fractions concluded that the reaction followed formal first order kinetics. The activation energies showed little variation with respect to particle size and the absence of any particle size effect on the rate of dehydration was attributed to the highly porous structure of the gel. The deviation from the ideal behaviour at the later stage of dehydration was interpreted on the basis of structure.

In the present investigation an attempt has been made to correlate activation energies of different particle sizes of silicic acid hydrogel.

Experimental

Silicic acid hydrogel was synthesised by cation exchange technique. After proper ageing, they were processed in accordance with reported method⁷ to remove the extraneous impurities. The particle size fractions ($-20+50$), ($-50+80$), ($-80+115$), ($-115+150$), ($-150+200$) and ($-200+300$) mesh were prepared with utmost precaution. The materials were again washed, dried and stored at $32 \pm 1^\circ$. The kinetics of the dehydration process was studied by TG method⁸.

Results and Discussion

The isothermal dehydration curves (Figures not shown) showed exponential behaviour and as such first order kinetics was suggested. The initial water concentration (L_∞) which can be dehydrated at the experimental temperature and also the rate constant k_1 for the initial stage of dehydration was calculated⁹ using equation (1)

$$\text{Log } \Delta L = \frac{-k_1 t}{2.303} + \text{log } L_\infty [1 - \exp(-k_1 \Delta t)]. \quad (1)$$

Where ΔL is the difference between the mass loss at time $(t + \Delta t)$ and t , time interval Δt